

Management

INFLUENCE OF WORK LIFE BALANCE ON PERFORMANCE OF EMPLOYEES IN JORDAN HOSPITALS

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Abstract

This paper examines the impact of WLB on performance of employees in Jordan hospitals. This study is a quantitative research and made use primary data using a research questionnaire as instrument was administered to a total number of 500 respondents selected from four governments and four privates hospitals namely: Al-Bashir hospital (Government), Al Mafraq Government Hospital (Government), Ram Manohar Lohia Hospital (Government), Jawaharlal Nehru Medical College (Government), Philadelphia hospital (private), Haramain Hospital (Private), Jordan hospital (private) and Fortis Hospital (Private) from Jordan. The result of the study reveals that impact of WLB on performance of employees was significant and joint impact of WLB and motivation significantly influence performance of employees. In conclusion, motivation plays an important role in encouraging employees to perform; a well-motivated employee has a possibility of performing better than an employee that is not well motivated.

Keywords: Work Life Balance; Employee Performance; Motivation, Performance.

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1. Introduction

The concept of Work life balance is a vital phenomenon and is of immense importance to different workers within public and private organizations. The phenomenon of Work Life Balance (WLB) is more than categorizing job functions and an individual's personal life. WLB equally determines the social, financial as well as psychological well-being of a person. These factors have been reflected in a worker's performance which influences the output of the individual at the place of work over a period of time. WLB has inference on workers' wellbeing, behavior and effectiveness of their companies Husain, U., & Javed, S. (2019) and Eby et al (2005). The drawbacks of WLB could affect the employer and workers. As for the workers, the outcome could trigger an adverse effect on their job, psychological wellbeing, physical health as well as performance within their companies Javed, S. (2018, Guest, (2001). As for employers the outcome of ineffective WLB could lead to absenteeism, poor output, stress, sick leave as well as high level of turnover among the workers and increase in cost of training and recruitment.

The concept of WLB is not just centered on childcare and families alone, neither is it on reduction in job functions. It is centered on working smart, being refreshed to contribute and give what is needed to work as well as home and not endangering any of the two. It is vital for all individuals; at any stage of life". (Khan, A. A., & Javed, S. 2017 and Sarfaraz, J. 2017) Stress reduction as well as absenteeism via the flexibility of an employer should not just give rise to a satisfied as well as effective performance within work force; it must equally have a knock-on influence on enhanced recruitment facilities as well as retention". The accomplishment of an effective WLB can give rise to dividends for employers based on having an effective motivated, diligent, minimized stressed workforce, enhanced productivity, as well as low level of absenteeism.

The concept of performance can be seen as combining various variables, like capacity, motivation, condition of work as well as anticipation (Briscoe & Schuler, 2004). According to Chandra & Frank (2004) and Khan, A., & Javed, S. (2016). performance evaluation systems are created to purposely assess the performance of employees as well as define steps needed to be taken in order to improve workforce, which is vital for the progress of an organization.

Another factor that affects the performance of employees is motivation. Ololube (2006) stated that motivations either intrinsic or extrinsic are vital to employees since they form the primary objective for working. Motivation connotes the complex forces and requirements that trigger the energy for a person to perform optimally (Shulze & Steyn, 2003). Javed, S., Atallah Aldalaieen, B., Husain, U., & Shahfaraz Khan, M. (2019) and Azar & Shafiqhi (2013) in their study noted that motivation will make workers of an organization to be more serious with their job and responsibilities. A good salary is an effective instrument that can play an important role in improving performance of employees and as well enhance an organization' level of productivity.

2. Objectives of The Study

The objectives of this study are as follows:

- 1) To determine the impact of WLB on performance of employees in Jordan hospitals.
- 2) To determine the impact of motivation and WLB on performance of employees in Jordan hospitals.

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses will be tested in this study:

Hypothesis One: H₀₁: There is a significant relationship between Work Life Balance and Employee Performance.

Hypothesis Two: H₀₂: Motivation and work life balance have a significant effect employee performance in Jordanian hospitals.

3. Literature Review

In a comparative work of private and public hospitals at Chennai India carried out by Lakshmi et al (2012), the authors examined the Work Life Balance of female nurses. The findings showed that 53 percent of the nurses were battling to attain WLB. In their study, Khan, A., Baseer, S., & Javed,

S. (2017) and Akram & Hassaan (2013) evaluated the influence of work-life conflict on job satisfaction among Pakistan doctors. Their result showed a significantly negative correlation between conflict (work-family intrusion as well as family-work intrusion) and satisfaction.

Ervin (2012) carried out a study on job satisfaction and WLB in Intercollegiate Athletic Graduate Supervisors and Assistants. The result showed that there was a significant difference within the groups.

4. Methodology

This study is a quantitative research and made use primary data using a research questionnaire as instrument was administered to a total number of 500 respondents selected from four governments and four privates hospitals namely: Al-bashir hospital (Government), Al Mafrqa Government Hospital (Government), Ram Manohar Lohia Hospital (Government),Jawaharlal Nehru Medical College (Government),Philadelphia hospital (private), Haramain Hospital (Private), Jordan hospital (private) and Fortis Hospital (Private) from India and Jordan respectively. The data collated was analyzed using SPSS and the hypotheses were analyzed using Multiple Regression Analysis (Albashabsheh,et al . (2018).

Hypothesis One: There is a significant relationship between Work Life Balance and Employee Performance

Table 1: Multiple Regression of Work Life Balance and Employee Performance

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta	B	Std. Error
1	(Constant)	-.378	.198		-1.904	.058
	WorkFamilyCulture	.095	.022	.139	4.270	.000
	Autonomy	.550	.054	.396	10.213	.000
	FlexibleWorkArrangement	.681	.033	.675	20.680	.000
	WorkLifeConflictReduction	-.215	.037	-.216	-5.846	.000
	WorkFamilyEnrichment	-.001	.009	-.002	-.114	.909

a Dependent Variable: Employee Performance

Table 2: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.950(a)	.903	.902	.71003

a Predictors: (Constant), Work Family Enrichment, Flexible Work Arrangement, Work Family Culture, Work Life Conflict Reduction, Autonomy

Table 3: ANOVA(b)

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	2306.513	5	461.303	915.028	.000(a)
	Residual	249.045	494	.504		
	Total	2555.558	499			

a Predictors: (Constant), Work Family Enrichment, Flexible Work Arrangement, Work Family Culture, Work Life Conflict Reduction, Autonomy
 b Dependent Variable: Employee Performance

The multiple regression results analysis shows that Work Life Balance (Work Family Culture, Flexible Work Arrangement, Autonomy, Reducing Work Life Conflict Work Life Enrichment) significantly jointly influenced Employee Performance [$R^2 = .903$; $F(5,499) = 915.028$; $p < .05$]. This infers that Work Life Balance (Work Family Culture, Flexible Work Arrangement, Autonomy, Reducing Work Life Conflict Work Life Enrichment) jointly accounted for about 90.3% of the variance observable in employee performance. Furthermore, the independent contribution of Work Family Culture, Flexible Work Arrangement, Autonomy and Reducing Work Life Conflict were significant ($\beta = .095$; $t = 4.270$; $p < .000$), ($\beta = .681$; $t = .675$; $p < .000$), ($\beta = .550$; $t = .396$; $p < .000$) and ($\beta = -.215$; $t = -2.16$; $p < .000$) while Work family enrichment was not significant. In addition, Work Family culture, autonomy and flexible work arrangement were positively significant while Reducing Work Life Conflict was negatively significant. This shows that WLB significantly influence employee performance.

Hypothesis Two: Motivation and work life balance have a significant effect employee performance in Jordanian hospitals.

Table 4: Multiple Regression of Motivation and Work Life Balance on Employee Performance

Table 4: Coefficients ^a					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	4.413	.544		8.109	.000
WLB	.107	.017	.297	6.142	.000
Motivation	-.173	.043	-.195	-4.027	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance

Table 5: ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	128.136	2	64.068	19.861	.000 ^b
	Residual	1603.272	497	3.226		
	Total	1731.408	499			

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Motivation, WLB

Table 6: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.272 ^a	.074	.070	1.796

a. Predictors: (Constant), Motivation, WLB

The multiple regression results analysis shows that Work Life Balance and motivation jointly significantly jointly influenced Employee Performance [$R^2 = .074$; $F(2,499) = 19.861$; $p < .05$]. This infers that Work Life Balance and motivation jointly accounted for about 7.4% of the variance observable in employee performance. Furthermore, the independent contribution of Work Life Balance and Motivation were significant ($\beta = .297$; $t = 6.142$; $p < .000$) and ($\beta = -.195$; $t = -4.027$; $p < .000$). In addition, work life balance was positively significant while motivation was negatively significant. This shows that both Work Life Balance and Motivation significantly influence employee performance.

5. Conclusion

The result of the first hypothesis shows a significant relationship between WLB and employee performance while the result of the second hypothesis showed that the joint effect of motivation and WLB on performance of employees was significant. This finding agrees with Kamau et al (2013) who examined WLB on Performance of employees in Eco bank, located at Kenya. The result of the study shows a correlation within performance of employees and WLB. Also, Dissanayaka et al (2013) who investigated the influence of WLB on performance of employee showed a positively significant correlation between WLB and employee performance. In conclusion, motivation plays an important role in encouraging employees to perform; a well-motivated employee has a possibility of performing better than an employee that is not well motivated.

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